

Emotional Intelligence and Self-esteem on Psychology Well-being in Adolescents with Divorced Parents

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Abstract

This research is motivated by the existence of divorce data that is common in Indonesia. The purpose of this study is to find out empirically whether there is an influence of emotional intelligence and self-esteem on psychological well-being in adolescents with divorced parents. This study involved 51 teenage participants with divorced parents. And this research uses purposive sampling technique. This data collection uses the satisfaction scales of psychological well-being, the emotional intelligence scale used in this study using scale (SEIS) compiled by Schutte, and the self-esteem scale used in this study using Rosenberg's scale. The results of this study indicate that there is a significant influence between emotional intelligence on psychology of well-being, and there is a significant influence between self-esteem on psychology of well-being. There is an effect between emotional intelligence and self-esteem together on psychology well-being of 48.9%.

Keywords: *emotional intelligence, self esteem, psychology well-being, and teenage*

INTRODUCTION

The family is the first and main place for children to receive education. The psychological satisfaction obtained by the child in the family will determine how he will react to the environment. On the other hand, the family is often a source of conflict for some people. A disharmonious family atmosphere often encourages conflict between the two parents. One of the things that is a big fear for a child is parental divorce. According to Ningrum (2013) how children react to their parents' divorce is strongly influenced by the way parents behave before, during and after divorce. The child will need greater support, sensitivity and compassion to help him cope with the loss experienced during the difficult time after his parents divorce.

Data from divorces are now plentiful. The age of marriage that is only as old as corn is prone to conflict that leads to separation. Deputy Minister of Religious Affairs Nasaruddin Umar admitted that the divorce rate is still high. Based on data from the Religious Courts (PA) nationally, the divorce rate in 2010 reached 314,354 at the first level. While based on the field, the number of divorces reached 284,379, namely the dominant divorce reached 190,280 and divorce divorce as much as 94,009 (Fimela, 2013). Meanwhile, according to statistical data, the divorce rate in 2015 has reached 347,256.

Research conducted by Kelly & Emery (2003) explains that parental divorce is believed on average to cause various behavioral and emotional problems in children and adolescents. According to Hurlock (2012) adolescence is an important phase for individuals for the formation of their personality. When parents and children have a positive and adaptive relationship, it will help adolescents in achieving optimal developmental tasks. Conversely, a disharmonious relationship between children and parents can have a negative effect on the lives of adolescents. One form of negative relationship can come from divorce that occurs in a family.

Demo, David and Alan (1996), explained that adolescents with a non-divorced parent background will have an impact on the development of psychological health in adolescents where it can improve adolescent psychological wellbeing. This is certainly inversely proportional to adolescents who have a divorced family background, not all aspects contained in psychological wellbeing can be achieved. According to the results of research conducted by Glenn & Krammer (1985), that parental divorce experienced by adolescents will result in feelings of discomfort, low self esteem, and several similar characteristics which ultimately lead to low psychological wellbeing. The effects experienced by adolescents will continue into adulthood.

According to Woolfolk (2008), however, divorce is something that is not easy for adolescents so it takes a process or stage that helps adolescents reach the stage of self-acceptance of parents' decision to divorce. Adolescents who

experience parental divorce tend to have no satisfaction in life, weak self-control, and no happiness (Amato & Sobolowski, 2001). Some of these things will later affect each dimension in psychological wellbeing.

In line with research conducted by Landa, Martos, & Lopez (2010) which states that individuals who are aware of what they feel will show the ability to manage emotional problems and to maintain or increase the intensity of positive emotions and to reduce or eliminate negative emotions, thus the individual will have psychological wellbeing. Ryff (1989) defines a person with psychological well-being (PWB) as an individual who has a positive attitude towards himself and others, is able to make decisions, is able to create and manage an environment that suits his needs, has a purpose in life and makes life meaningful, as well as, strives to explore and develop himself.

Dagun (2002) explains that a divorce event that occurs to parents has an impact on adolescents such as emotional instability, experiencing anxiety, depression, and frequent anger. Laver & Laver (2000) argue that the family has shaped a person's personality since childhood and continues to have a huge influence on a person's behavior, attitudes and thoughts in adulthood. This is supported by the theory of Robert Weiss (1974), which states that children's emotional reactions are highly dependent on the child's understanding of his or her parents' marriage, the child's age, the child's temperament and the parent's attitude and behavior towards the child. Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand one's own feelings and the feelings of others, and the ability to motivate oneself and others (Goleman, 2005). This is in line with the opinion expressed by Agustian (2003), which states that emotional intelligence is the ability to feel, understand, and effectively apply emotional power and sensitivity as human energy, information, connection, and influence.

The results of Carmeli's (2003) research on the relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being state that there is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological well being. This is because individuals who have high emotional intelligence will be more careful in resolving conflicts than individuals with low emotional intelligence.

In addition to emotional intelligence, another factor that affects psychological well-being in adolescents with divorced parents is self-esteem. Therefore, the role of both parents is very important in the formation of self in adolescents, one of which is the formation of self-esteem (Wangge & Hartini, 2013). The formation of self-esteem in children whose parents are divorced is not easy, especially in adolescence who still really need support from the environment. In adolescence, when they are dealing with serious and severe problems, behavioral changes are evident in them. During adolescence, adolescents' feelings are

inconsistent. According to Blascovich and Tomaka (1991), self-esteem is an

individual's view of his or her value or how a person assesses, recognizes, appreciates or likes himself or herself. Self-esteem is one of the factors that determine individual behavior. Everyone wants a positive appreciation of himself, so that someone will feel that he is useful or meaningful to others even though he has weaknesses.

Research conducted by Rahmawati, Handarini, and Triyono (2017) which examines the relationship between self-esteem and psychological well-being concluded that self-esteem significantly has a positive influence on psychological wellbeing. This is because someone who has high self-esteem will also have high psychological well-being. Individuals with high self-esteem can be detected by having several aspects such as meaningfulness, strength, ability, and goodness. These four aspects can make individuals accept themselves, relate positively to others, be independent, have environmental autonomy, have life goals, and pass the growth phase well.

Based on the previous explanation, the purpose of this study is to examine the effect of emotional intelligence and self-esteem on psychological well-being in adolescents with divorced parents.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study involved 51 adolescents with divorced parents as participants. The participants in this study were males and females aged 11-20 years old, consisting of 8 males and 43 females.

Psychology well-being is a condition in which individuals have a positive attitude towards themselves and others, can make their own decisions and regulate their own behavior, can create and manage an environment that suits their needs, have a purpose in life and make their lives more meaningful, and try to explore and develop themselves (Ryff, 1989). The psychological well-being scale used in this study uses the Ryff scales of psychological well-being which has been modified by the researcher. The Ryff scales of psychological well-being measure five dimensions of psychological wellbeing consisting of, self acceptance, positive relations with others, autonomy, environmental mastery, purpose in life, personal growth. One example of an item in this scale is "I know my feelings because I experience them". The answer options range from very appropriate to very inappropriate. This scale consists of 20 items with a reliability of 0.811.

Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand one's own feelings and the feelings of others, and the ability to motivate oneself and others (Goleman, 2005). The emotional intelligence scale used in this study uses the scale (SEIS) compiled by Schutte et al (1998). SEIS is measured based on four factors, namely, perception of emotion, managing own emotions, managing other's emotions,

and utilization of emotion. One example of an item in this scale is “I wish I could appreciate myself more”. The answer options range from Very Appropriate to Very Inappropriate. This scale consists of 10 items with a reliability of 0.834.

Self-esteem is an evaluation one has about oneself, either positive or negative (Rosenberg, 1965). The self-esteem scale used in this study uses Rosenberg's (1965) scale. One example of an item on this scale is “I tend to worry about what other people think of me”. The answer options range from Very Appropriate to Very Inappropriate. This scale consists of 20 items with a reliability of 0.818.

The data obtained in this study will be analyzed statistically using multiple linear regression analysis techniques. Data analysis aims to determine the effect of emotional intelligence (X1) and self-esteem (X2) on psychological well-being (Y). Data analysis was carried out using the help of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 22 for Windows program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis testing is done using multiple regression. The results show a significance of 0.000 ($p > 0.001$) which indicates that the significant results in the emotional intelligence variable, and self-esteem can be used to predict psychological well being.

Table 1. Regression Test Results Emotional Intelligence, Self Esteem on Psychology well being

F	Sig	R Square
0.699	0.000	0.489

The results of the correlation coefficient between psychology well-being variables, emotional intelligence and self-esteem show the results of $R = 0.699$ and the coefficient of determination (R^2) = 0.489. This means that the variables of emotional intelligence and self-esteem together contribute 48.9% while 51.1% is another factor outside this study. The results of hypothesis testing using multiple regression analysis show an F value of 0.699 with a significance of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). This means that there is a significant influence between emotional intelligence and self-esteem together on psychological well being in adolescents with divorced parents.

In this study, emotional intelligence variables have a higher influence on psychological wellbeing.

Dagun (2002) explains that a divorce event that occurs to parents has an impact on adolescents such as emotional instability, experiencing anxiety, depression, and

frequent anger. This is supported by the theory of Weiss (1974), which states that children's emotional reactions are highly dependent on children's understanding of their parents' marriage, children's age, children's temperament and parents' attitudes and behavior towards children. Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand one's own feelings and the feelings of others, and the ability to motivate oneself and others (Goleman, 2005).

This is in line with the opinion expressed by Agustian (2003), which states that emotional intelligence is the ability to feel, understand, and effectively apply emotional power and sensitivity as human energy, information, connections, and influence. According to research conducted by Mayer (2009), it explains that individuals who have emotional intelligence will be able to maintain a positive mentality caused by their ability to control emotional activity by recognizing, understanding, awakening, regulating, and promoting. Thus it can be concluded that individuals who have high emotional intelligence will have high psychological well-being. This is in line with research conducted by Putri (2013), emotional intelligence has an influence on self-confidence. Emotional intelligence can also have an influence on the development of one's achievements. This is in line with the dimension of psychological well being, namely environmental mastery, where self-confidence is needed to master the environment in which one lives. In addition, self-confidence is needed in achieving other dimensions of psychological well being, namely life goals in the form of achievement in order to develop one's self.

The second influence that has a role in psychological well being is self-esteem. The formation of self-esteem in children whose parents are divorced is not easy, especially in adolescence who still really need support from the environment. In adolescence, when they are dealing with serious and severe problems, behavioral changes are evident in them. During adolescence, adolescents' feelings are inconsistent. According to Rosenberg (1965), self-esteem is an evaluation of oneself, both positive and negative. The same thing is reinforced in research conducted by Schilling (2015), which shows that students with high self-esteem are assumed to have higher psychological well-being in all subscales of psychological well-being. The findings of the study have important implications for understanding that self-esteem affects psychological well-being. Further research conducted by Susanti (2012), which explains that self-esteem can affect psychological well-being. This is seen from the aspect of self-esteem, namely, individuals who have power over their environment will be able to interpret themselves positively. This is in accordance with the similarity between the dimensions of self-esteem and the dimensions of factors that affect psychological well-being.

CONCLUSIONS

Emotional intelligence and self-esteem jointly contribute to psychological well being in adolescents with divorced parents. Then the role of emotional intelligence was found to have a higher influence on psychological well being in adolescents with divorced parents.

ADVICE

Future researchers can take a larger sample size, then for further research that wants to examine emotional intelligence, self-esteem and the influence of these variables on psychological well being to pay more attention to other variables that have not been measured in this study.

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